

Fluoride contamination of ground water in Birbhum, West Bengal

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Abstract : Fluoride is known to contaminate ground water reserves globally. High fluoride content in ground water has been reported from various parts of India as well as in West Bengal. Fluoride pollution in India is mainly due to natural sources reported so far. High concentration of fluoride in ground water is due to the percolation of water through fluoride rich rock and leaching out of fluoride from these rocks. Ground water is the major source of drinking water and at low levels of fluoride contamination causes serious health problems which is difficult to cure. So, the present study was carried out to determine the fluoride content of ground water in five blocks of Birbhum district in West Bengal. Ground water samples were collected from shallow and deep tube wells and hot water spring of different locations. Fluoride was observed in the ranges of 2.88–9.36 ppm, which was above the permissible limits of 1 ppm.

Keywords : Fluoride, water pollution, Birbhum.

Introduction

Presence of fluoride in water is a public health problem in most of the Indian states. Ground water forms a major source of drinking water in urban as well as rural areas. Fluoride contamination in ground water of several States in India has been reported^{1,2} including West Bengal³. Contamination of fluoride in the ground water is a natural phenomenon, influenced basically by the local and regional geography as well as hydrogeological conditions. The amount of fluoride occurring naturally in ground water is governed principally by climate, composition of host rock and hydrogeology⁴. Though fluoride enters the body through food, water, industrial exposure, drugs, cosmetics etc., drinking water is the major contributor⁵.

Contamination of fluoride in the ground water and resultant diseases has become a global problem. India is facing the same problems and the problem of high fluoride concentration in ground water resources has become one of the most important toxicological⁶ issues in India.

The aim and objectives of the study was (i) to determine the fluoride content of ground water in Birbhum district, West Bengal, (ii) to find out the probable cause

of fluoride contamination and (iii) to compare the fluoride content of different sources of ground water.

Materials and method :

This present study was carried out in Birbhum district of West Bengal. The study area lies between 23°32'30" to 24°35'0" north latitude and 88°1'40" to 87°5'25" east longitude.

Collection of ground water sample : Water sample was collected from shallow and deep tube wells, hot springs from different blocks of Birbhum districts namely : Nalhati, Rampurhat, Bolpur, Dubrajpur, Suri.

Analysis of the sample : Fluoride concentration measured by standard procedure⁷ is given below.

Principles :

Total solubilized fluoride is determined potentiometrically using a fluoride ion selective electrode in conjunction with a standard single junction reference electrode and a pH meter with an expanded millivolt scale being calibrated directly in terms of fluoride concentration.

Reagents :

(a) Standard (Std.) fluoride solution 0.1 mg/L, 1 mg/L, 10 mg/L.

(b) TISAB buffer (Total ionic strength adjustment buffer).

57 ml glacial acetic acid, 58 g NaCl and 4 g CDTA were added in 500 ml distilled water and the pH 5.3–5.5 was adjusted with 6 (N) NaOH and volume was made to 1 L with distilled water.

Procedure :

Distillation of sample :

200 ml sample was taken and made alkaline with NaOH solution using phenolphthalein concentrated to 50 ml on a steam bath avoiding loss of sample by splashing. It was transferred quantitatively to the distillation flask after cooling. The distillation flask was connected to the steam distillation apparatus. 50.0 ml of 1 : 1 H₂SO₄ was carefully added in it. Silver sulphate was added to the sample in distillation at the rate of 5 mg per mg of chloride in the sample. Then the steam distillation was started at temperature between 135–145 °C. The temperature was constant throughout the distillation. The distillate was collected in 250 ml Tarson flask up to 250 ml. A blank was carried out in the same manner.

Analysis :

50 ml 0.1, 1, 10 mg/L standard fluoride solution and 50 ml TISAB were taken and the instrument was calibrated. 50 ml distilled sample and 50 ml TISAB were taken and stirred the solution at constant rate and concentration was read directly from the display.

Calculation :

$$\text{Fluoride (mg/L)} = \frac{\text{Fluoride (mg/L)} \times \text{Volume of distillate in ml}}{\text{Original sample (ml)}}$$

Statistical analysis : The statistical analysis was performed on all data in the present study using SPSS 11.5 and independent sample 't' test was done to find out significant difference of fluoride content in ground water collected from different sources.

Results and discussion

Chemical composition of surface or subsurface, geothermal or non-thermal is one of the major factors on which the suitability of the water for domestic, industrial and agricultural purpose depends. During weathering and circulation of water in rocks and soils, fluorine is leached out and dissolved in ground water. The high fluoride values in West Bengal in water may be due to leaching of fluoride from the hornblende gneiss and granulites⁸. During weathering and circulation of water in rocks and soils, fluorine is leached out and dissolved in ground water. Table 1 shows fluoride concentration in ground water from different location of Birbhum district, West Bengal. Tables 2, 2A and 2B show significant difference of fluoride content in ground water collected from different sources.

The permissible limit of fluoride, according to US Environmental Protection Agency, in drinking water is 1

Table 1. Fluoride concentration in ground water from different location of Birbhum district, West Bengal

Block	Sl. No.	Location	Source	Fluoride concentration (ppm)
Nalhati	1.	Nalhati B.D.O.	Deep tube well	3.58
	2.	Bautia (Uttarpara)	Deep tube well	4.88
	3.	Bautia High School	Deep tube well	4.46
	4.	Bautia (Dakshinpara)	Deep tube well	5.16
	5.	Nasipur	Shallow tube well	3.48
	6.	Nasipur	Shallow tube well	5.12
	7.	Bhabanandapur	Shallow tube well	3.4
	8.	Bhabanandapur	Shallow tube well	3.38
	9.	Kansal	Shallow tube well	4.42
	10.	Kansal	Deep tube well	4.52
	11.	Kansal	Deep tube well	3.6

Table-1 (contd.)

Rampurhat	12.	Saralpur	Deep tube well	5.44	
	13.	Saralpur	Shallow tube well	5.28	
	14.	Dangapara	Shallow tube well	5.02	
	15.	Nabagram	Shallow tube well	5.34	
	16.	Saralpur	Deep tube well	5.08	
	17.	Kabichandrapur	Shallow tube well	5.14	
	18.	Atla	Deep tube well	4.86	
	19.	Atla Riverside	Shallow tube well	5.18	
	20.	Atla	Shallow tube well	5.1	
	21.	Atla Primary School	Shallow tube well	5	
	Bolpur	22.	Bhubandanga (Kabitirtha Hotel)	Shallow tube well	3.4
		23.	Bhubandanga (Word No. 8)	Shallow tube well	2.88
		24.	Bolpur Power House	Shallow tube well	3.32
		25.	Word No. 18	Shallow tube well	3.06
		26.	Word No. 18	Shallow tube well	3.22
		27.	Word No. 5	Shallow tube well	3.56
		28.	Bolpur Primary Health Centre	Shallow tube well	3.36
		29.	Bolpur Station	Shallow tube well	3.24
	Dubrajpur	30.	Ward No. 1	Deep tube well	3.38
		31.	Rathtala	Deep tube well	3.32
		32.	Dubrajpur	Deep tube well	3.52
33.		Ward No. 11	Deep tube well	3.46	
34.		Hetampur Health Home	Deep tube well	2.96	
35.		Hetampur Tantipara	Deep tube well	3.36	
36.		Hetampur College	Deep tube well	3.36	
37.		Pahareswar Road	Deep tube well	3.28	
38.		Pahareswar Temple	Deep tube well	3.16	
39.		Baganpara	Deep tube well	3.64	
40.		Khayerban	Deep tube well	6.2	
41.		Ward No. 8	Deep tube well	3.68	
42.		Bakreshwar (Panchanan Villa)	Deep tube well	4.2	
43.		Gohaliwara Gram	Deep tube well	4.66	
44.		Bakreshwar (Agnikundu)	Hot water spring	9.1	
45.		Bakreshwar (Baitarni Ganga)	Hot water spring	9.06	
46.		Bakreshwar (Brahmakundu)	Hot water spring	9.36	
Suiri		47.	New Dangalpara	Deep tube well	4.38
		48.	J. L. Banerjee Road	Deep tube well	4.6
	49.	Jilla School	Deep tube well	4.24	
	50.	Ward No. 9	Deep tube well	4.48	

Fig. 2. Comparative study of ground water collected from deep and shallow tube well

Parameters	Ground water from		Significant level
	Deep tube well	Shallow tube well	
Fluoride (ppm)	4.15 ± 0.83	4.10 ± 0.92	NS

Fig. 2A. Comparative study of ground water collected from deep tube well and hot water spring

Parameters	Ground water from		Significant level
	Deep tube well	Hot water spring	
Fluoride (ppm)	4.15 ± 0.83	9.17 ± 0.13	$P < 0.001$

Fig. 2B. Comparative study of ground water collected from shallow tube well and hot water spring

Parameters	Ground water from		Significant level
	Shallow tube well	Hot water spring	
Fluoride (ppm)	4.10 ± 0.92	9.17 ± 0.13	$P < 0.001$

ppm. Birbhum district and some specific parts of this area – particularly Nalhati, Rampurhat, Bolpur, Dubrajpur, Suiari are found to be extremely polluted with fluoride ground water (Table 1). Fluorine appears in almost every kind of rocks, therefore it is exposed to weathering and transport to ground water. Geochemically, tropical environments are unique and these uniqueness stems from the fact that these terrains are continuously subjected to extreme rainfall and drought with resulting strong geochemical fractionation of elements. This characteristic geochemical partitioning results in either severe depletion of elements or accumulation to toxic levels⁹. Geologist believes that probable origin of excess is volcanic eruption of basaltic composition.

Fig. 1. Showing difference in fluoride concentration (ppm) of water from different sources.

It was revealed from the study that fluoride concentration in hot spring was significantly higher than deep and shallow tube well where as no significant difference was observed between shallow and deep tube well. Ground water, especially hot springs are richer in fluorine and enrichment can be explained by longer contact times between rocks and water, higher temperature and high pH values. A study by Kundu *et al.*¹⁰, reported that high

concentration of fluoride in ground water in Singhpur and Sagaragan village in Nayagarh district of Orissa was mainly due to presence of hot spring and its interaction with surrounding ground water and surface water.

Our result was similar to the study of Gupta *et al.*³, who reported that the source of this fluoride contamination in ground water at Nasipur may be due to the presence of intertrappean sedimentary beds that were initially enriched in fluoride and became soluble in entrapped water due to favourable physico-chemical conditions and entrapped water may percolate and dissolve locally concentrated pockets of highly soluble villiaurite (NaF) with in the volcanic trap rock during its journey from secondary aquifer to the surface.

Conclusions

So, it might be concluded from the study that fluoride concentration in water of shallow and deep tube wells, hot springs of Birbhum is above the permissible limit may pose health risk to humans.

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